

Industrial Production and clinical application of L-asparaginase: A Chemotherapeutic Agent

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Abstract : This article comprises detail information about L- asparaginase, encompassing topic such as various sources of L- asparaginase, mechanism and properties of L- asparaginase. Also describe the production, cultivation and purification of L- asparaginase along with information about the application of L- asparaginase. L- asparaginase catalyses the conversion reaction to convert asparagines to aspartic acid and ammonia. Asparagine is a nutritional requirement for both normal and tumor cell. Present scenario has found that L- asparaginase has been found to be a best anti tumor or antileukemic agent. In the recent years these enzyme gained application in the field of clinical research pharma and food industry. It has been characterized based on the enzyme assay principle hydrolyzing L- asparaginase into L- aspartic acid and ammonia. It has been observed that eukaryotic micro organism such as yeast and filamentous fungi have a potential for L- asparaginase production. L- asparaginase has been and is still one of the most lengthily studied therapeutic enzymes by scientist and researchers worldwide.

Keywords : L- asparaginase, Antitumor, Solid state fermentation, chemotherapeutic.

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